

Anthropometry of Nigeria Young Adult for the Development of Radiation PhantomOlaseni M. Bello^{1,2}, Jamo H. U.³, Kehinde Omotosho¹, Jerry Manga Yusuf¹¹*Department of Physics, Nigeria police Academy, Wudil, Kano*²*Department of Physics, University Technology Malaysia, UTM, Johor Bahru, Malaysia*³*Department of Physics, Kano University of Science and Technology, Kano*

Abstract-: Nigeria is a spectacular country, with a perfect blend of diverse rich cultures; ethnic groups and multi-talented people. Nigeria is home to about 218.5 million people; and these people spread over six (6) geo-political zones. The geo-political zones subdivides into thirty-six (36) States, one (1) Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and 744 Local Government Areas (LGA). The population of young adult (18-24years) in Nigeria is 25million, constituting 11.4% of Nigeria total population with 52% male and 48% female. In terms of population distribution, 60% of the young adults reside in the urban areas while 40% reside in the rural areas/suburbs. The median age is 17.2years. On education, 40% are educated up to tertiary level, 35% are educated up to secondary/high school, and 15% of the population are engaged in vocational or technical education while the remaining 10% had no formal education. 60% of the young adult population are students, 20% are employed on part or full time basis, and 5% are self-employed while 15% are unemployed. Among the employed category, 40% are low income earners while middle and high income are 30% apiece. English language literacy among young adults in Nigeria is 90% while the remaining 10% perfectly speak only the local language fluently. Data are collected randomly from 18 states, which constitute 50% of the states in the country. The measurements taken from the sampled young adults in each state include the height (cm), the mass (kg), length (cm) of the arm, the length head and neck, the torso length and the length of the leg. The overall mean values obtained include 20.55years for age, 66.94kg for mass, 172.00cm for height, 87.65cm for the arm length, 25.96cm for the length of the head and neck, 49.15cm for the trunk, 98.56cm for the leg and 22.63 for the BMI. Various equations were derived to relate the height to the other measured parts of the body, the equations however have low predictive capabilities; efforts are in progress to improve on the equations. For the development of the radiation phantom, the mean values above were used to modify an existing and available MCNPTM computational code of AMALETM phantom of Oak Ridge National Laboratory. A peculiar radiation phantom code was developed for the interim purpose of radiation planning in Nigeria. This research study is considered a pilot study with a view of a thorough anatomical investigation of the Nigerian Man in future.

Keywords: Anthropometry, Nigeria Young Adult, BMI, Radiation Phantom

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1.0 Introduction

Nigeria is a spectacular country, with a perfect blend of diverse rich cultures; ethnic groups and multi-talented people. Nigeria is home to about 218.5 million people [1]; and these people spread over six (6) geo-political zones. The six geopolitical zones are south-west, south-east, south-south, north-west, north-east and north-central. The geo-political zones subdivides into thirty-six (36) States and one Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. This population-spread further sub-divided into 744 Local Government Areas

(LGA), with each LGA arranged in ten (10) to twenty (20) wards; depending on the size of the LGA. Nigeria operates federal system of government whereby the head of the federal government is an elected president. The state, the LGA and the ward are managed by elected governor, chairman and councilor respectively. Nigeria has so many notable natural deposits and many worthy tourist reserves, these reserves favorably compare with any standard reserve in the world. Nigeria boast of so many outstanding universities, research centers, polytechnic and colleges. Graduation of outstanding scholars

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from these institutions is a continuum; and with emphasis on excellence, the impact of these human resources are felt globally.

Health-care delivery in Nigeria is outstanding, with teaching hospitals and specialist hospitals well spread across the country. General hospitals are strategically located in every locality and private hospitals abound in rural and urban areas. Medical imaging facilities are established in all the public medical facilities. These medical imaging facilities are mostly the X-radiography facilities, which uses ionizing radiation to achieve health diagnostic or therapeutic imaging success. Hence, it is reasonable to plan the imaging procedure in advance in order to reduce the risk due to radiation hazard, this is the area of interest of this study. The focus of this study is on the anthropometry of young adults in Nigeria, the data from this anthropometry study is useful for the development of an intermediary code that is used for radiation planning. The target sample of this research is Nigeria young adults (18-24years) which constitute 11.4% of the total population of the country; and they are 90% educated. This literacy level of the young adult is a promising report on Nigeria future literacy rate, as these young adults approach their old age.

Anthropometry is a core concern in this research study, it is basically the measurements of the human body and it is mostly used to assess changes in populations of different samples [2] [3]. It is the measurement of dimension of human body such as girths, skinfolds, lengths and breadths using landmark surfaces for reference [4]. These measurements entails the weight, the height, the body mass index (BMI), the head circumference and neck [5], the body circumference covering the measurements of the hip, waist and limbs [2]. Dynamic anthropometry has also been investigated and compared to stationary anthropometry data [6]. These measurements have proven to be very resourceful and of high importance in their applications in various fields of research. These fields of researches cover a wide range of research in sciences (computational and information sciences, physical sciences, medical and general health sciences, research application to radiation sciences and so on); management and social sciences, liberal art and even law. In this study, the anthropometry data collected is useful in modifying a radiation phantom, an

important and useful tool in effective radiation planning procedure.

1.1 Relevance and Applications of Anthropometry Studies

In this study, anthropometry measurements were taken from male young adults (18-24years). Measurements from sampled volunteers were taken and recorded based on the states of origin of male volunteers. This provide an opportunity to ascertain the peculiar measurements of each state and each geo-political zones in Nigeria. These collected data were infused into the computational code of the existing AMALE™ radiation phantom, modifying the code to yield a peculiar Nigeria Adult Male Phantom Computational Code

The applications of measured anthropometry data are diverse [7] and are reported in several publications. Hand anthropometry has been used to estimate grip strength and hand functional assessment [8]. Hand anthropometry has also been measured extensively and applied to hand tool designs and machine-human interactions [9]. Anthropometry measurement has been reportedly used for the assessment of nutritional health status in children, it was described as easy, non-invasive and low-cost approach in measurement of health status [10] [11] [12] [13].

Evaluation of the effect of the maternal anthropometry on infant anthropometry has also been conducted [14]. The applications in digital anthropometry, a machine learning tool, confirmed that anthropometry approach is cheap, in-field with enhanced accuracy, high validity and hands-on practical [3]. Augmented, Virtual and Mixed Reality researches have adopted the utilities of anthropometry measurements in the design of head mounted devices [15]. Anthropometry is also applicable in sport science [16] [17]. Anthropometry studies has also been reported in its application to neonatal birth studies to monitor maternal changes in order to accommodate the increment in fetal demands [18]. Ear morphology anthropometry has been carried out to investigate the variations in the ear dimension of young adults [19]. In Nigeria, anthropometry procedures has been used to investigate the dietary and nutritional status of adolescent Nigerians [20] and to compare Nigeria adolescents blood pressure based on gender [21]. Several other reported cases [22] [23] [24] [25] affirm the acceptable utility of

anthropometry concepts in diverse areas of research. In this study, anthropometry data is used to modify an existing radiation phantom. Radiation phantoms are ghost-like computational and/or physically molded structure, meant to mimic the human body for the purpose of establishing appropriate radiation planning procedure before a radiation based medical imaging/therapeutic procedure is carried out. Radiation phantoms are designed to possess the radiological properties of the human body.

1.2 Demography of Nigeria Young Adult (18-24years)

The population of 18-24years young adult in Nigeria is 25million, 11.4% of Nigeria total population with the distribution: 52% male and 48% female. These young adults spread across 36 States and the Federal Capital Territory. In terms of population distribution, estimated 60% of the young adults reside in the urban areas while 40% reside in the rural areas/suburbs. The median age is 17.2years. On education, 40% are educated up to tertiary level, 35% are educated up to secondary/high school, and 15% of the population are engaged in vocational or technical education while the remaining 10% had no formal education. And 60% of the young adult population are students, 20% are employed on part or full time basis, 5% are self-employed while 15% are unemployed. Among the employed category, 40% are low income earners while middle and high income are 30% apiece. English language literacy among young adult in Nigeria is 90% while the remaining 10% perfectly speak only the local language fluently. With this projection, Nigeria will attain approximate full literacy rate in the next 25-30years when the present young adults attain old age and the present old people are approximately no more in existence. The young adult in Nigeria within the age range 18-24years are mostly single (90%), 5% married (married population is 38% more in the rural areas than the urban areas), 2% divorced or separated, and 3% widowed. It is an estimated fact that 7.2% of this age group have their first birth at 18years. The religious position of this population assert that 55% are Christians, 45% of the population are Muslims while 5% practices traditional religion or other religions. 50% of the young adults in Nigeria have access to good health care facilities, 25% are engaged in regular exercise and 20% rely on healthy eating habits. [26] [1] [27].

1.3 Radiations

In nature, there are natural substances that emit radiations when exposed; these substances are mostly buried deep inside the earth. However, some substances that share similar characteristics are artificially produced in the laboratory. This substances are referred to as radioactive sources or substances. The radiation produced from a radioactive source is electromagnetic in nature, it is highly penetrating, invisible and very ionizing. Ionizing mean that, on exposure of radioactive sources; radiations that are emitted have the capability to cause biological damage to living tissues or organs if the emission of the radiation is not controlled. It should however be clearly noted that if the emission of radiation from a radioactive source is adequately controlled, the emitted radiation is a very useful and resourceful tool in scientific investigations, discoveries and milestone achievements.

There are four different types of radiation; namely the alpha particle, the beta, the gamma ray and X-ray. The alpha particle is the heaviest with the lowest energies, slowest and less penetrating. When alpha particle travels through matter, it dwells more with the substance of the matter because it is slow and less penetrating; hence, it interacts more with the matter and by so doing it ionizes more and causes more biological damage. The beta particle is faster and more penetrating than the alpha particle, but with higher energies. The beta particle dwell less with the substance of the matter when it passes through matter; hence, causing less biological damage as it passes through the matter. The gamma ray is more energetic compared to beta and alpha. Gamma ray and X-ray are electromagnetic rays with high penetration power and less biological damage because it dwell less with the substance of the matter as it travels through the substance of the matter. However, X-ray and gamma ray could be dangerous or hazardous if it continuously passes through matter, prolonging the interaction time with the traversed matter. The high penetrating capability of radiation made radiation a very useful tool to see inside a closed matter; for instance, scanning through the inside of a human body without dissecting the human body.

The applications of the usefulness of these emitted radiations cut across all fields of scientific innovations. In medicine, it is used to access the internal parts of the human body and

assess the health status; without the option of surgery. It is in line with this capability of radiations that made medical radiation scientist design a computational ghost like structure to mimic the human body. This ghost like structure is referred to as radiation phantom. It could be computational (computer code) or physical, it is however mostly a computational code that tends to aid easy subjection of the human phantom to radiations and relevant calculations are done. These calculations are referred to radiation planning procedures. The radiation planning procedure helps to establish a balanced judgment and to minimize the radiation dose risk to humans in a real-life human exposure to radiations during radiation diagnostic or therapeutic procedure.

1.4 Radiation Phantom

The radiation phantom is a computational code (computer program), prepared to mimic the human body when the program build up. This is simply a ghost-like structure of the human body. On the computer graphic user interface, GUI, of the code builder platform; the phantom is a 3-dimensional structure in which all the parts of the human body are represented by their 3-D coordinates. The belly button is taken as the origin (0, 0, 0), so all the other parts of the body takes their respective (x, y, z) coordinates.

In this study, an existing radiation phantom is adopted as a reference. This reference radiation phantom is called AMALE™, an MCNP™ computational code; where AMALE and MCNP are registered trademark of the Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA. In this study, the AMALE™ phantom is modified with the anthropometry data obtained from Nigeria young adult, to produce a modified AMALE computational code that is peculiar to Nigeria young adult.

2.0 Material and Method

In this study, two stage approach was adopted: The first stage is the anthropometry data collection and analysis, the second stage is the application of the anthropometry data in modifying the radiation phantom. The anthropometry measurements taken in this study include the height in centimeter , the mass in kilogram, the length of the arm, the length of the leg, the length of the torso, and the vertical length of the head and neck, These measurements were applied in the second stage

of the study to modify the existing computational code AMALE™ phantom. The resultant computational code is a computational phantom code peculiar to the Nigeria young adult male population.

A survey of young adults between 18years and 24years were sampled from 18 states chosen at random from the 36 states of the Federation. Measurements were taken using meter rule to measure the length or height and recorded in centimeter, cm; MI Fit weighing balance was used to measure the mass in kilogram, kg and collected data analysis was achieved with Microsoft Excel. These analysis include the estimation of the mean (average) of the collected data, estimation of the Body Mass Index, BMI; and the estimation of the standard deviation, variance, standard error and the relative error in the data collected.

Equations

$$\text{Mean, } \bar{X} = \frac{\sum_i^N X_i}{N}$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation, } \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{(\sum(X_i - \bar{X})^2)}{(N - 1)}}$$

$$\text{Variance, } \sigma^2 = \frac{(\sum(X - \bar{X})^2)}{(N - 1)}$$

$$\text{Standard Error, } SE = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}}$$

$$\text{Relative Error} = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{X}\sqrt{N}} = \frac{SE}{\bar{X}}$$

$$BMI = \frac{M}{H^2}$$

4.0 Results and Discussion

The mean values obtained in the last row of Table 1 represent a unique set of values peculiar to Nigeria Young Adult and it will be used to modify the existing radiation phantom as stated for the second stage procedure.

The lowest mean age (years) obtained from the sampled states population was recorded as 19.40 years for Oyo state while Kebbi state recorded the maximum mean of the sampled age with 22.80 years. The mean age for 18-24 years Nigeria Young Adult obtained in this study is

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20.55 years. The mass measured in kilogram, kg has highest mean value of 76.47kg recorded as the mean value for Oyo state sampled population while the lowest value is recorded by Katsina (61.14kg). The case of Oyo is spectacular as Oyo recorded the lowest sampled age and the highest mass, which confirmed the likelihood of Oyo state emergence with almost the highest Body Mass Index, BMI. In Table 1, the height was recorded in meters, m to enable easy calculation

of BMI. However, the height was recorded in centimeter, cm when plotting the bar chart in order to establish a balance for easy comparison. Ogun state recorded the highest height of 181cm, followed by Kebbi with 176cm and then, Oyo and Borno with a record of 175cm. Four states recorded the lowest height of 167cm; the states are Ekiti, Bauchi, Gombe and Kwara.

Table1: Mean Values and BMI per State

	Mean Value							
	age	Mass	Height	Arm	Head & Neck	Trunk	Leg	BMI
Oyo	19.40	76.47	1.75	90.80	25.20	50.20	99.50	25.08
Ekiti	20.50	64.73	1.67	82.40	24.50	41.20	96.80	23.24
Edo	20.00	67.38	1.72	81.20	25.60	51.40	96.80	22.72
Ogun	20.30	70.63	1.81	93.70	26.90	52.60	105.40	21.51
Ondo	21.11	68.29	1.73	90.11	25.56	49.79	99.44	22.90
Plateau	21.60	67.07	1.73	87.30	27.0	48.40	96.9.0	22.33
Nasarawa	20.60	74.66	1.70	92.90	25.70	48.60	97.80	25.83
Kogi	20.10	65.22	1.73	94.40	25.90	49.40	96.70	21.79
Sokoto	20.40	61.28	1.72	84.90	26.40	46.70	99.00	20.71
Borno	19.80	67.03	1.75	89.50	25.90	48.00	100.10	21.89
Taraba	20.90	70.05	1.74	84.40	26.10	46.70	98.40	23.14
Zamfara	21.60	67.07	1.73	87.30	27.00	48.40	96.90	22.41
Bauchi	19.60	62.80	1.67	84.80	24.70	50.60	96.50	22.52
Katsina	20.60	61.14	1.70	89.60	26.20	51.40	98.90	21.16
Kano	19.50	67.13	1.71	86.60	25.80	48.40	99.20	22.96
Gombe	20.70	58.31	1.67	85.9	26.5	48.2	98.9	20.83
Kebbi	22.80	70.25	1.76	91.00	27.1	52.2	100.1	22.68
Kwara	20.30	65.487	1.67	80.80	25.2	52.5	95.0	23.62
Mean	20.55	66.94	1.72	87.65	25.96	49.15	98.56	22.63

The BMI is a parameter calculated from the mass of the body and the height, it is dimensionally a measure of the mass per unit area of the body since it is the

mass per square of the height (kg/m²), the unit of the height must however be in meters, m. It is a measure of the distribution of the mass over the entire

body height. It is used as a yardstick to assess/measure how healthy an individual is, it is directly linked to obesity to ascertain the health status of diabetic patients.

Nasarawa state recorded the highest BMI with 25.83, followed by Oyo state 25.08 and the lowest BMI was recorded by Katsina with a BMI of 21.16; the mean BMI obtained for the Nigeria Young Adult from this study was recorded as 22.63

Figure 2: Resultant Mean Values Obtained for Nigeria Young Adult

In Nigeria, [21] [28] assert that BMI < 18.5 is classified as underweight and it is equivalent to low risk of diabetes, BMI = 18.5 – 24.9 is classified as normal weight and it is equivalent to moderate risk of diabetes while BMI = 25.0 – 29.9 is classified as over-weight and it is equivalent to high risk of diabetes. However, BMI ≥ 30.0 is classified as obese and it is equivalent to a very high risk of diabetes. It should however be emphasized that BMI is not the only factor considered in confirming diabetic status of patient, other important factors might include age, family medical history, blood pressure and the level of patients engagement in physical activities.

In a normal human being, there is a conservation of body equivalence that tends to make the body structure appear normal; without which the body will appear

abnormal. This informed the fact that to every human body height, there is an appropriate and equivalent body part length that make the physique normal.

Proposed theory: When the growth and development of a living thing is normal, there exist a mathematical relationship between the body parts; in terms of the respective volume, area or length.

So therefore, the values of the height is considered related to the measured lengths of every parts in the body. In this study, this relationship is expressed with equations. From Table 1 obtained in this study, the linear plot of the arm (cm) versus the height (cm) using the scattered points (Figure 3) was used to generate an equation that relates the arm-length (cm) to the height (cm). The

polynomial equation (equation 3.1) that relate the measured height to the approximate estimate of the arm length with predictive accuracy of 36% (R^2 -value) is:

$$y \cong 0.0038x^2 - 0.6516x + 85.875 \quad \dots 3.1$$

$y = \text{Arm Length, cm} \quad x = \text{Height, cm}$

Figure 3: Arm Length (cm) Versus Height (cm)

The equation 3.1 above is a relation between the height (cm) of a Nigerian Young Adult and the corresponding arm length (cm). With a known height, the arm length could be determined.

The comparison of the height (cm) and neck & head (cm) is achieved and presented in

Figure 4. The equation that relate the head & neck and the height with the highest predictive accuracy of 37% (R^2 -value) is the 2nd order polynomial given as equation 3.2:

$$y \cong 0.0005x^2 - 0.0859x + 24.842 \quad \dots 3.2$$

$y = \text{Head \& Neck, cm} \quad x = \text{Height, cm}$

Figure 4: Head & Neck Versus Height, cm

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In a similar manner, effort was made to establish a relationship between the trunk and the height; and the leg and the height but no equation provide predictive capability beyond 1%.

The equation 3.1 and equation 3.2 relates the arm length, and the head & neck to the height. Hence, if the height is determined; the various arm lengths and head & neck are easy to estimate.

Plotting the mass versus the square of the height yield a slope that is equivalent to the best value of the BMI. However, the value

obtained from the graph is lower compared with the value obtained from the mean values. The BMI obtained from the model graph is approximately 19.84 and R-squared value of 0.3078 compared to the mean value of 22.63. R-squared value is a prediction of how well the equation predict the outcome of the dependent variable. Hence, the R-squared value of the prediction is just 30.78% which is considerably low. It is therefore reasonable to accept the mean value obtained from the field.

$$y = 19.835x + 8.2412. \quad \dots 3.3$$

$$R^2 = 0.3078$$

Figure 7: Mass (kg) Versus Height-Square

4.1 Development of the Radiation Phantom

The relevant data used for the modification of AMALETM radiation phantom to achieve a peculiar phantom for Nigeria Radiation Phantom are the mean values obtained in Table 1.

The AMALETM MCNPTM computational code is available in this report as appendix B. MCNPTM is a state of the art trade mark

radiation code of Oak Ridge National Laboratory.

To achieve successful modification, it is wise to modify the leg code line of the AMALE code. The reason is that, when other parts like the trunk or head & neck are tampered with; so many hidden organs are destroyed unknowingly. From the last row of Table 1, the mean values are:

	Age	Mass	Height	Arm	Head & Neck	Trunk	Leg	BMI
Mean	20.55	66.94	172.00	87.65	25.96	49.15	98.56	22.63

These values, in the interim constitute the reference values for Nigeria Young Adult; the values are used to develop a

computational radiation code for the age group.

4.1 Phantom Modification

The modification is achieved by way of selective reduction in length. AMALETM phantom is a typical Caucasian, the length of the leg is approximately 80cm, appendix B.

For the AMALE, a short section of the AMALETM MCNPTM code containing modified lines is

```

.....
.....
64 3 -1.04 ((171 -5)(172 -170)(-119 169)(313 413)) 43 44
imp:p=1 $ male genitalia
65 0 -2:-7:8:-9:10:15 imp:p=0
c end of cell Cards
    
```

c Surface Cards
 1 s 0 -100 91.45 1
 2 pz -300.0
 4 pz -80.0
 5 pz 0.0
 6 pz 70.0
 7 px -1000.0
 8 px 1000.0
 9 py -1000.0
 10 py 1000.0
 11 sq 100 400 0 0 0 0 -40000 0 0 0 \$trunk-skin
 12 pz 91.45
 13 gq 1 1 0 0 0 -0.2 -20 0 0.04 3.96 \$ left leg
 213 gq 1 1 0 0 0 0.2 20 0 0.04 3.96 \$ right leg
 313 gq 1 1 0 0 0 -0.2 -20 0 0 0 \$ left leg skin
 413 gq 1 1 0 0 0 0.2 20 0 0 0 \$ right leg skin

14 sq 100 64 0 0 0 0 -6400 0 0 0 \$head1-skin
 15 pz 200.0

....
 However, the modified surface cards are:

4 pz -80.0
 5 pz 0.0
 20 pz -79.8

The adjusted surface card code lines for the modified male are:

4 pz -99.5

 20 pz -99.5

Figure10: AMALE

Figure 11: Modified Phantom

Despite the fact that an average Caucasian (AMALE data) is 180cm in height, their legs are an average of 80cm. From this study, an average Nigeria Young Man is 172cm but

the legs are 99cm long. This shows that an average Caucasian has longer trunk plus head and neck (~100cm) than an average Nigerian (~73cm)

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4.2 Future Plans and Direction

This study constitute a pilot study of the anthropometry status of the young adults in Nigeria, it is the plan of the researcher to embark on the investigation into the full-fledged anthropometry of the Nigeria population in not too distant future. This future study is intended to be achieved in collaboration with experts in various fields like radiation science, medical imaging, medical physics, anatomy, nutrition, human kinetic, biochemistry, microbiology and many more relevant fields. With the stated volume of the

research, the researcher hope to achieve this future study with partial collaborative support and/or using government sponsorship and/or using external grant.

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Appendix

MCNP Code for AMALE™ Phantom

c Input file of ORNL phantom - Adult male (Eckerman et al., 1996)
c Cell Cards
1 1 -1.87 -1 imp:p=1 \$source
4 3 -1.04 ((-13 20 -5):(-213 20 -5)) #21 imp:p=1 \$ legs
5 2 -0.00129 (((313 4 -5 413):-4):(11 5 -6):(21 6 -22): &
(14 22 -12):(24 12 -15)) 1 2 7 -8 9 -10 #64 #15 imp:p=1
Soutsides of phantom
6 3 -1.04 ((-23 6 -22 114) #44 #18 #118):(-21 22 -322
114):(322 -12 -18 116) &
#41 #43 #17):((-524 12 116) #43 #42) imp:p=1 \$ head
and neck
7 3 -1.04 (-5 20 -313 13):(213 -413 -5 20):(4 -20 -313):(4 -20
-413): &
(-11 16 5 -19):(-11 19 -6 21): &
(-21 23 6 -22):(22 -322 21 -14):(-14 18 322 -12):(12 -24
524) imp:p=1 \$skin
8 4 -0.296 (-27:28:-29:30) -25 31 imp:p=1 \$right lung
9 4 -0.296 (33:34:32) -26 31 imp:p=1 \$left lung
10 3 -1.04 -35 36 -37 -38 imp:p=1 \$liver
11 3 -1.04 -39 40 #47 imp:p=1 \$stomach
12 3 -1.04 -40 imp:p=1 \$ contents
13 3 -1.04 -41 42 imp:p=1 \$ urinary bladder
14 3 -1.04 -42 imp:p=1 \$ contents
15 3 -1.04 (-43):(-44) imp:p=1 \$ testes
17 3 -1.04 -45 imp:p=1 \$brain
18 3 -1.04 (-48 175 37 -19):(-176 177 -178) #41 imp:p=1
\$esophagus:thoracic+abdominal portion
118 0 -175 37 -19 imp:p=1 \$ void in esophagus
19 3 -1.04 (-49 50 51 -52):(-53 54 -55 56):(-57 58 59 -52):(-
61 62 -59 65): &
(-63 64 -65 5) imp:p=1 \$colon:ascending, transverse,
descending and sigmoid
20 3 -1.04 (-50 51 -52):(-54 -55 56):(-58 59 -52):(-62 -59
65): &
(-64 -65 5) imp:p=1 \$contents-colon
21 5 -1.4 (-66 20 -5):(20 -5 -67) imp:p=1 \$ leg bones
24 5 -1.4 (-68 5 -70 -16):(-69 5 -70 -16) imp:p=1 \$ arm
bones
25 5 -1.4 (-71 272 -72 -119):(-71 -73 -273 -119) imp:p=1
\$clavicles
26 5 -1.4 (75 -74 78 -79 119 80 -81):(75 -74 78 -79 119 -76
77) imp:p=1 \$scapulae
28 5 -1.4 ((-83 82 -86 87 5 -85):(82 -83 87 85 -84)) imp:p=1
\$pelvis
29 5 -1.4 ((-75 89 90 -91):(-75 89 92 -93):(-75 89 94 -95):(-
75 89 31 -96): &
(-75 89 97 -98):(-75 89 99 -100):(-75 89 101 -102):(-75
89 103 -104): &
(-75 89 105 -106):(-75 89 107 -108):(-75 89 109 -110):(-
75 89 111 -79)) &
#10 #24 #25 #26 imp:p=1 imp:p=1 \$rib cage
41 5 -1.4 (-112 84 -90):(-112 90 -19):(19 -113 -114) imp:p=1
\$spine
c 41 5 -1.4 -112 84 -90 imp:p=1 \$spine, lower portion
c 411 5 -1.4 -112 90 -19 imp:p=1 \$ spine, middle portion
c 412 5 -1.4 19 -113 -114 imp:p=1 \$ spine, upper portion
42 5 -1.4 -116 45 -12 #18 imp:p=1 \$skull-cranium
43 5 -1.4 (-116 45 12 #18):(118 -117 120 -121 -119 116)
imp:p=1 \$facial skeleton
44 3 -1.04 (((-125 134 -122 6 -133 123 127):(-126 128 -122
123 -134 6 -133)): &
((-129 131 134 -122 123 133 -47):(-130 132 -134 -122
123 133 -47))) &
-122 123 -23 -124 6 -47) imp:p=1 \$thyroid
45 3 -1.04 (-135 65):(-136 -137) imp:p=1 \$ kidneys

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47 3 -1.04 (-138 139 -65):(-138 65 140) imp:p=1 \$pancreas
 48 3 -1.04 -141 imp:p=1 \$spleen
 49 3 -1.04 -142 imp:p=1 \$thymus
 50 3 -1.04 (-143 145):(-144 145) imp:p=1 \$ adrenals
 52 3 -1.04 (-146 147 -148):(-149 150 148 -348) imp:p=1 \$gall bladder
 53 3 -1.04 (-147 -148):(-150 148 -145) imp:p=1 \$gall bladder-contents
 54 3 -1.04 -151 152 153 #56 #57 imp:p=1 \$heart -left ventricle
 55 3 -1.04 -152 153 #56 #57 imp:p=1 \$ heart-left ventricle-contents
 56 3 -1.04 -154 155 153 -156 151 imp:p=1 \$right ventricle
 57 3 -1.04 -155 153 -156 151 imp:p=1 \$right ventricle-contents
 58 3 -1.04 (-157 158 -153 156):(-159 160 -153 -156) imp:p=1 \$left atrium-part 1 and 2
 59 3 -1.04 (-158 -153 156):(-160 -153 -156) imp:p=1 \$contents of the left atrium
 60 3 -1.04 -161 162 -153 -156 159 imp:p=1 \$right atrium
 61 3 -1.04 -162 -153 -156 159 imp:p=1 \$contents-right atrium
 62 3 -1.04 ((-82 164 -165 52 -36):(-82 49 164 -165 166 -52)) #19 #20 imp:p=1 \$small intestine
 63 3 -1.04 ((-16 5 -19):(-19 -6 -21 114)) #8 #9 #10 #11 #12 #13 #14 & #18 #19 #20 #24 #25 #26 #28 #29 & #41 #45 #47 #48 #49 #50 #52 #53 #54 #55 & #56 #57 #58 #59 #60 #61 #62 #118 imp:p=1 \$trunk
 64 3 -1.04 ((171 -5):(172 -170):(-119 169)(313 413)) 43 44 imp:p=1 \$ male genitalia
 65 0 -2:-7:8:-9:10:15 imp:p=0
 c end of cell Cards

 c Surface Cards
 1 s 0 -100 91.45 1
 2 pz -300.0
 4 pz -80.0
 5 pz 0.0
 6 pz 70.0
 7 px -1000.0
 8 px 1000.0
 9 py -1000.0
 10 py 1000.0
 11 sq 100 400 0 0 0 0 -40000 0 0 0 \$trunk-skin
 12 pz 91.45
 13 gq 1 1 0 0 0 -0.2 -20 0 0.04 3.96 \$ left leg
 213 gq 1 1 0 0 0 0.2 20 0 0.04 3.96 \$ right leg
 313 gq 1 1 0 0 0 -0.2 -20 0 0 0 \$ left leg skin
 413 gq 1 1 0 0 0 0.2 20 0 0 0 \$ right leg skin
 14 sq 100 64 0 0 0 0 -6400 0 0 0 \$head1-skin
 15 pz 200.0
 16 sq 96.04 392.04 0 0 0 0 -37651.521 0 0 0 \$trunk
 18 sq 96.04 60.84 0 0 0 0 -5843.0736 0 0 0 \$head1
 19 pz 69.80
 20 pz -79.8
 21 cz 5.4
 22 pz 78.40
 322 pz 78.6
 23 cz 5.20 \$neck
 24 sq 5112.25 3271.84 6400 0 0 0 -327184 0 0 91.45 \$head2
 524 sq 4638.172 2938.72 5843.074 0 0 0 -282235.1 0 0 91.45 \$head2
 25 sq 32400 14400 1406.25 0 0 0 -810000 -8.50 0 43.50 \$right lung
 26 sq 32400 14400 1406.25 0 0 0 -810000 8.50 0 43.5 \$ left lung
 27 pz 46
 28 pz 54

29 px -5.4
 30 py 1.5 \$ end the section removed from the right lung
 31 pz 43.5
 32 pz 55
 33 px 8.0
 34 py 1.0 \$end the section removed from the left lung
 35 sq 64 272.25 0 0 0 0 -17424 0 0 0 \$liver
 36 pz 27
 37 pz 43
 38 p 0.028571 0.022222 -0.023256 -1 \$end def the liver
 39 sq 576 896 144 0 0 0 -9216 8 -4 35 \$ stomach-wall
 40 sq 310.914543 625.988841 65.363490 0 0 0 -3566.739812 8 -4 35 \$ stomach-contents
 41 sq 142.988120 293.942933 293.942933 0 0 0 -3514.900218 0 -4.50 8 \$urinary bladder-wall
 42 sq 105.646247 227.630725 227.630725 0 0 0 -2339.687839 0 -4.50 8 \$bladder-contents
 43 sq 11.9025 8.9401 3.8025 0 0 0 -20.115225 -1.30 -8 -2.30 \$testes-left
 44 sq 11.9025 8.9401 3.8025 0 0 0 -20.115225 1.30 -8 -2.30 \$testes-right
 45 sq 2445.3025 1440.2025 3221.6976 0 0 0 -106517.3769 0 0 91.45 \$brain
 c 37 pz 43.0
 47 pz 75.0
 48 sq 0.1764 1.3689 0 0 0 0 -0.24147396 0 2.575 0 \$esophagus: thoracic+abdominal portion
 175 sq 0.0144 0.7569 0 0 0 0 -0.01089936 0 2.575 0
 176 5 cx 0.70
 177 5 px 0.10
 178 5 px 7.80
 49 sq 6.25 6.25 0 0 0 0 -39.0625 -8.50 -2.36 0 \$ULI- upper large intestine 1.ascending colon-wall
 50 sq 3.20947225 3.20947225 0 0 0 0 -10.300712135 -8.5 -2.36 0 \$ascending colon-contents
 51 pz 14.45
 52 pz 24.0 \$end ac. col.
 53 sq 0 2.25 6.25 0 0 0 -14.0625 0 -2.36 25.50 \$ ULI 2.transverse colon-wall
 54 sq 0 0.946729 3.892729 0 0 0 -3.68539433441 0 -2.36 25.50 \$ transverse colon-contents
 55 px 10.50
 56 px -10.50
 57 gq 0.282933 0.220415 0.00663757 0 0.0721253 -0.0288859 -4.541008 -0.628932 & 0.128904 17.669146 \$LLI-lower large intestine 1. descending colon-wall
 58 gq 0.556917 0.395554 0.0120398 0 0.129435 -0.056858 -8.938371 -1.128675 & 0.271613 35.669768 \$descending colon-contents
 59 pz 8.72
 c 52 pz 24.0
 61 ty 3.0 0 8.72 5.72 1.57 1.57 \$LLI 2. sigmoid colon -upper
 62 ty 3.0 0 8.72 5.72 0.91 0.91
 63 ty 3.0 0 0 3.0 1.57 1.57 \$sigmoid colon -lower
 64 ty 3.0 0 0 3.0 0.91 0.91 \$sigmoid colon -lower
 65 px 3.0
 66 gq 1 1 0.00906872 0 0 -0.200501 -20 0 1.78571 87.75 \$left leg bone
 67 gq 1 1 0.00906872 0 0 0.200501 20 0 1.78571 87.75 \$right leg bone
 68 gq 0.510204 0.137174 0 0 0 0.010352 -19.4898 0 -0.204969 185.878 \$left arm bone
 69 gq 0.510204 0.137174 0 0 0 0.010352 18.0612 0 0.175983 159.592 \$right arm bone
 70 pz 69
 71 tz 0 11.1 68.25 20 0.7883 0.7883 \$clavicles
 72 p 0.89415 1 0 11.1
 73 p -0.89415 1 0 11.1

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272 p 7.0342 1 0 11.1
 273 p 7.0342 -1 0 -11.1
 75 sq 94.09 289 0 0 0 0 -27192.01 0 0 0 \$scapulae
 c 75 sq 96.04 361 0 0 0 0 -34670.44 0 0 0
 74 sq 95.8441 289 0 0 0 0 -27698.94 0 0 0
 76 p 0.25 -1 0 0 \$left
 77 p 0.80 -1 0 0
 78 pz 50.9
 79 pz 67.3
 80 p 0.25 1 0 0 \$right
 81 p 0.80 1 0 0
 82 sq 127.69 127.69 0 0 0 0 -16304.7361 0 -3.8 0 \$pelvis
 83 sq 144 144 0 0 0 0 -20736 0 -3 0
 84 pz 22
 85 pz 14
 86 py 5
 87 py -3
 c 75 88 sq 96.04 289 0 0 0 0 -27755.56 0 0 0 \$rib cage
 89 sq 86.49 272.25 0 0 0 0 -23546.9025 0 0 0
 90 pz 35.1
 91 pz 36.5
 92 pz 37.9
 93 pz 39.3
 94 pz 40.7
 95 pz 42.1
 c 31 pz 43.5
 96 pz 44.9
 97 pz 46.3
 98 pz 47.7
 99 pz 49.1
 100 pz 50.5
 101 pz 51.9
 102 pz 53.3
 103 pz 54.7
 104 pz 56.1
 105 pz 57.5
 106 pz 58.9
 107 pz 60.3
 108 pz 61.7
 109 pz 63.1
 110 pz 64.5
 111 pz 65.9
 c 79 pz 67.3
 112 sq 6.25 4 0 0 0 0 -25 0 5.50 0 \$ spine-mid, lower
 113 pz 84.8
 114 sq 6.25 4 0 0 0 0 -25 0 1.45 0 \$ spine-upper
 c 45 sq 2445.3025 1440.2025 3221.6976 0 0 0 -106517.3769
 0 0 91.45 \$skull -cranium
 116 sq 3991.080625 2487.515625 5076.5625 0 0 0 -
 224498.28515625 0 0 91.45 \$skull-cranium
 117 sq 81 49 0 0 0 0 -3969 0 0 0 \$ facial skeleton
 118 sq 57.76 31.36 0 0 0 0 -1811.3536 0 0 0 \$facial skeleton
 c 80 sq 5112.25 3271.84 6400 0 0 0 -327184 0 0 91.45 \$the
 statements defining the cranium
 119 py 0.0
 120 pz 82.4
 121 pz 93.13
 122 c/z 0 -4.0 2.2 \$thyroid
 123 c/z 0 -4.0 1.0
 124 py -4
 125 gq 1 1 -0.531464 -2 0 0 -8 8 78.9413 -2915.4 \$thyroid
 (inside R)
 126 gq 1 1 -0.531464 2 0 0 8 8 78.9413 -2915.4 \$thyroid
 (inside R)
 127 gq 1 1 -0.109807 -2 0 0 -8 8 16.3102 -589.661 \$thyroi
 (outside r)
 128 gq 1 1 -0.109807 2 0 0 8 8 16.3102 -589.661 \$thyroid
 (outside r)

129 gq 1 1 -0.0590516 -2 0 0 -8 8 7.34563 -212.437
 \$thyroid (inside R)
 130 gq 1 1 -0.0590516 2 0 0 -8 8 7.34563 212.437 \$thyroid
 (inside R)
 131 gq 1 1 -0.0122007 -2 0 0 -8 8 1.51769 -31.1977 \$thyroid
 (outside r)
 132 gq 1 1 -0.0122007 2 0 0 8 8 1.51769 -31.1977 \$thyroid
 (outside r)
 133 pz 71.25
 134 px 0
 135 sq 68.0625 612.5625 45.5625 0 0 0 -1378.265625 6.0 6.0
 32.50 \$left kidney
 136 sq 68.0625 612.5625 45.5625 0 0 0 -1378.265625 -6.0
 6.0 32.50 \$right kidney
 c 65 px 3
 137 px -3
 138 sq 15.6816 2787.84 368.64 0 0 0 -4014.4896 -1.0 0 37
 \$pancreas
 139 px -1
 140 pz 37
 141 sq 144 441 49 0 0 0 -1764 11 3 37 \$spleen
 142 sq 10.24 36 1.44 0 0 0 -23.04 0 -7.30 57.00 \$thymus
 143 1 sq 6.25 56.25 0.5625 0 0 0 -14.0625 0 0 0 \$ left adrenal
 144 2 sq 6.25 56.25 0.5625 0 0 0 -14.0625 0 0 0 \$ right
 adrenal
 145 1 pz 0
 146 3 so 2.12 \$ gall bladder
 147 3 so 2.0 \$ gall bladder
 148 3 pz 0
 348 3 pz 8
 149 3 sq 1 1 -0.05175625 0 0 0.4823 -4.4944 0 0 0 \$ gall
 bladder
 150 3 sq 1 1 -0.05175625 0 0 0.455 -4 0 0 0 \$ gall bladder
 151 4 sq 240.25 710.7556 1849 0 0 0 -17768.89 0 0 0 \$
 HEART left ventricle
 152 4 sq 44.3556 172.6596 729.5401 0 0 0 -2363.709924 0 0
 0 \$left ventricle (wall+contents)
 153 4 px 0
 154 4 sq 1225 3624.08 1849 0 0 0 -90601 0 0 0 \$ right
 ventricle (wall+contents)
 155 4 sq 792.9856 2621.44 1239.04 0 0 0 -50751.0784 0 0 0
 \$ right ventricle
 156 4 pz 0
 157 4 sq 240.25 280.2276 729 0 0 0 -7005.69 0 0 0 \$left
 atrium (wall+contents)-part 1
 158 4 sq 173.1856 203.9184 574.5609 0 0 0 -4504.557456 0
 0 0 \$ left atrium (wall+contents)-part 1
 159 4 sq 110.25 128.5956 729 0 0 0 -3214.89 0 0 0 \$ left
 atrium (wall+contents)-part 2
 160 4 sq 71.5716 84.2724 574.5609 0 0 0 -1861.577316 0 0 0
 \$ left atrium (wall+contents)part 2
 161 4 sq 1225 1428.84 729 0 0 0 -35721 0 0 0 \$ right atrium
 162 4 sq 991.6201 1167.5889 574.5609 0 0 0 -25792.038801
 0 0 0 \$ right atrium (wall+contents)
 c 82 163 sq 127.69 127.69 0 0 0 0 -16304.7361 0 -3.80 0
 \$small intestine
 164 py -4.86
 165 py 2.20
 166 pz 17
 c 36 pz 27 \$end small intestine
 171 pz -4.8 \$male genitalia
 172 p 1 0 0.1 -10 \$xz plane
 170 p 1 0 -0.1 10
 169 p 0 1 0.1 -10 \$yz plane
 c end surface cards
 vol j 20800 j 5250 2890 1810 1560 1830 152 250 45.7 203
 37.6 1370 44.7 j &

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372.5 360.9 2800 956 54.7 202 606 694 983 618 305 19.9
 288 &
 90.7 176 20.1 15.7 10.1 53.6 177 102 67.2 108 31.6 115
 27.4 &
 111 1060 43090 196 j
 tr1 3.5 5.0 38 0.616 0.788 0 -0.788 0.616 0 0 0 1
 tr2 -3.5 5 38 0.616 -0.788 0 0.788 0.616 0 0 0 1
 tr3 -4.5 -3.2 30 0.9615 0 -0.2748 -0.0574 0.9779 -0.2008
 0.2687 0.2090 0.9403
 tr4 1 -1.8 50 0.6751 -0.4727 -0.5664 -0.4640 0.3249 -0.8241
 0.5736 0.8191 0
 tr5 0 2.575 42.30 0.736084 -0.604969 -0.303634 0.634945
 0.772557 0 0.234575 &
 -0.192791 0.952789
 c Material Cards
 m1 55137 1.0 \$source
 m2 7000 0.8 8000 0.2 \$air
 m3 1000 10.454E-02 6000 22.663E-02 7000 2.490E-02
 8000 &
 63.525E-02 11000 0.112E-02 12000 0.013E-02 14000
 0.030E-02 &
 15000 0.134E-02 16000 0.204E-02 17000 0.133E-02
 19000 &
 0.208E-02 20000 0.024E-02 26000 0.005E-02 30000
 0.003E-02 &
 37000 0.001E-02 40000 0.001E-02 \$soft tissue
 m4 1000 10.134E-02 6000 10.238E-02 7000 2.866E-02
 8000 &
 75.752E-02 11000 0.184E-02 12000 0.007E-02 14000
 0.006E-02 15000 &
 0.080E-02 16000 0.225E-02 17000 0.266E-02 19000 &
 0.194E-02 20000 0.009E-02 26000 0.037E-02 30000
 0.001E-02 &
 37000 0.001E-02 \$lung
 m5 1000 7.337E-02 6000 25.475E-02 7000 3.057E-02 8000
 &
 47.893E-02 9000 0.025E-02 11000 0.326E-02 12000
 0.112E-02 14000 0.002E-02 &
 15000 5.095E-02 16000 0.173E-02 17000 0.143E-02
 19000 &
 0.153E-02 20000 10.190E-02 26000 0.008E-02 30000
 0.005E-02 &
 37000 0.002E-02 38000 0.003E-02 82000 0.001E-02
 \$skeleton
 mode p
 c Source Cards
 sdefcel 1 par 2 erg d1 pos 0 -100 91.45 rad d2
 si1 1 0.661
 sp1 d 0.851
 si2 0 1
 sp2 0 1
 c Tally Cards
 fc4 tally for average photon flux in the cell 8
 f4:p 8 \$lungs
 fc6 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 8
 f6:p 8 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 8
 fc14 tally for average photon flux in the cell 7
 f14:p 7 \$skin
 fc16 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 7
 f16:p 7 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 7
 fc24 tally for average photon flux in the cell 10
 f24:p 10 \$liver
 fc26 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 10
 f26:p 10 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 10
 fc34 tally for average photon flux in the cell 11
 f34:p 11 \$stomach and contents
 fc36 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 11 and 12
 f36:p 11 12 t \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell
 11 and 12

fc44 tally for average photon flux in the cell 13 and 14
 f44:p (13 14) \$bladder and contents
 fc46 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 13 and 14
 f46:p 13 14 t \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell
 13 and 14
 fc54 tally for average photon flux in the cell 15
 f54:p 15 \$testes
 fc56 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 15
 f56:p 15 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 15
 fc64 tally for average photon flux in the cell 17
 f64:p 17 \$brain
 fc66 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 17
 f66:p 17 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 17
 fc74 tally for average photon flux in the cell 18
 f74:p 18 \$esophagus
 fc76 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 18
 f76:p 18 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 18
 fc84 tally for average photon flux in the cell 19 and 20
 f84:p (19 20) \$colon and contents
 fc86 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 19 and 20
 f86:p 19 20 t \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell
 19 and 20
 fc94 tally for average photon flux in the cell 21
 f94:p 21 \$leg bones
 fc96 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 21
 f96:p 21 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 21
 fc104 tally for average photon flux in the cell 24
 f104:p 24 \$arm bones
 fc106 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 23
 f106:p 24 t \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 24
 fc114 tally for average photon flux in the cell 25
 f114:p 25 \$clavicles
 fc116 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 25
 f116:p 25 t \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 25
 fc124 tally for average photon flux in the cell 26
 f124:p 26 \$scapulae
 fc126 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 26
 f126:p 26 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 26
 fc134 tally for average photon flux in the cell 28
 f134:p 28 \$pelvis
 fc136 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 28
 f136:p 28 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 28
 fc144 tally for average photon flux in the cell 28
 f144:p 29 \$rib cage
 fc146 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 29
 f146:p 29 \$tally energy deposition
 fc154 tally for average photon flux in the cell 41
 f154:p 41 \$spine
 fc156 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 41
 f156:p 41 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 41
 c f354:p 411 \$spine
 c fc356 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 411
 c f356:p 411 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell
 411
 c fc354 tally for average photon flux in the cell 411
 c f454:p 412 \$spine
 c fc456 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 412
 c f456:p 412 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell
 412
 fc164 tally for average photon flux in the cell 42
 f164:p 42 \$skull-cranium
 fc166 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 42
 f166:p 42 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 42
 fc174 tally for average photon flux in the cell 43
 f174:p 43 \$facial skeleton
 fc176 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 43
 f176:p 43 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 43
 fc184 tally for average photon flux in the cell 42 and 43
 f184:p (42 43) \$skull

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fc186 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 42 and 43
f186:p (42 43) \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell
42 and 43
fc194 tally for average photon flux in the cell 44
f194:p 44 \$thyroid
fc196 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 44
f196:p 44 \$tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 44
fc206 tally energy deposition averaged over SKELETON
f206:p (21 24 25 26 28 29 41 42 43)
fc216 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 45 -
kidneys
f216:p 45 \$kidneys
fc226 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 47
pancreas
f226:p 47 \$pancreas
fc236 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 48 splen
f236:p 48 \$splen
fc246 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 49 thymus
f246:p 49 \$thymus
fc256 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 50 -
adrenals
f256:p 50 \$adrenals
fc266 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 52 and 53
gall bladder
f266:p (52 53) \$gall bladder
fc276 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 54-61
heart
f276:p (54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61) \$heart
fc286 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 62 small
intestine
f286:p 62 \$ small intestine
fc296 tally energy deposition averaged over a cell 64 male
genitalia
f296:p 64 \$ male genitalia
nps 100000000
phys:p 0.661 0 0